

Influence of Compost Fertilizer and Gibberellic Acid Priming of Bulbs on the Growth and Flowering of Daffodil (*Narcissus tazetta* L.) Plants

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Abstract

Supplementing horticultural crops with non-synthetic fertilizers such as compost and plant growth promoters such as gibberellic acid is a promising environment-friendly strategies to enhance the vegetative growth and flowering characteristics of horticultural crops including cut-flowers. This study aimed to find out the effect of soil application of compost fertilizer and bulb priming with gibberellic acid on different plant growth parameters and flowering age of *Narcissus daffodil* plants. Three levels of compost (0, 15 and 30% of the soil mix) and gibberellic acid (0, 50 and 100 mg L⁻¹) were applied to bulbs of *Narcissus tazetta* in a pot experiment. Results of the study showed a significant effect of adding compost fertilizer and soaking bulbs with gibberellic acid on all the plant growth parameters and flowering age of daffodil plants. Particularly, 30% compost application and soaking bulbs in 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid solution exhibited maximum plant height (38.19 and 36.83 cm, respectively), per plant leaf numbers (4.82 and 4.89 leaves, respectively), emergence duration (9.18 and 9.38 days, respectively), leaf length (52.74 and 54.68 cm, respectively) and width (2.31 and 2.35 cm, respectively) and flowering age (15.04 and 13.03 days, respectively) of plants as compared to control and other treatments. Moreover, the binary application of both treatments (30% compost plus 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid) showed a synergistic effect on all plant growth traits suggesting the incorporation of these non-synthetic fertilizer and plant growth promoters for enhancing the production of *N. Tazetta* daffodils and other cut-flowers.

Keywords: *Daffodils, Narcissus tazetta, Compost fertilizer, Gibberellins, Vegetative growth.*

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Introduction

Floriculture constitutes as one of the important sectors of horticultural plant production that contributes significantly to the farmers' income by producing different flowering and non-flowering ornamental plants (Adebayo et al., 2020). These plants such as cut-flowers are being exported to many other

countries, especially those famous for growing cut-flowers, such as the Netherlands, France, Belgium, Greece, and others (Hurrell, 2016; Faust & Dole, 2021). Among flowering ornamental plants *Narcissus* holds significance in different ethnic backgrounds and rituals. Daffodils were frequently planted near tombs by the Greeks. These white colored daffodil flowers are often seen as a symbol of goodness and purity (Liu & Liao, 2025).

The genus *Narcissus* L. belongs to the monocotyledon plant family Amaryllidaceae that is a family of flowering perennial plants. *Narcissus* is one of the main cut-flowers with beautiful cluster flowers, being primarily used in landscaping and ornamental exhibitions (Maryam & Gul, 2025). These are also important medicinal and aromatic plants, as their extracts and essential oils are employed on commercial scale for perfumery, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries (Breiterová et al., 2020). Daffodil plants contain many chemical compounds including cinnamyle, eugenol, benzaldehyde, alcohols and benzoic acid (Groom, 2012; Boshra et al., 2022). *Narcissus*-derived benzaldehydes exhibit significant anti-cancer and anti-tumor properties (Mazumder et al., 2020; Ibrahim et al., 2022).

The bulbous plants of *Narcissus* can live and adapt themselves according to the changing growth conditions. *Narcissus* bulbs are valuable geophytes for micropropagation of *Narcissus* cultivars but lengthy dormant phase of these bulbs is the major challenge (Lee & Elston, 2023). A variety of plant growth regulators have been shown to boost various plant metabolic processes such as seed germination, plant growth and development (Al-Khafaji, 2014; Farman et al., 2019; Carlos et al., 2021). Plant growth regulators have a major role in the growth and development of plants. Gibberellins, particularly gibberellic acid (GA3), are one of the plant growth promoters as they activate the vegetative growth by increasing the expansion and division of cells, activating metabolic and physiological processes, and activating the work of enzymes such as alpha-amylase and carboxylases (Asami & Nakagawa, 2018; Kosakivska & Vasyuk, 2021). Gibberellic acid is one of the most important plant hormones that plays a major role in regulating plant metabolism and cellular reproduction (Shah et al., 2023). It is an essential phytohormone which regulates different plant physiological processes such as vegetative growth, flowering, stimulation of leaf area expansion, biomass production, ions transport and stem elongation, seeds germination capabilities and seedling growth and development (Muniandi et al., 2018; Lupepsa et al., 2024). Gibberellic acid is also known to break the seed and bulb dormancy in ornamental plants including daffodils (Situma et al., 2015; Jokar & Asil, 2021).

Moreover, the excessive use of chemical fertilizers leads to human health hazards and environmental contamination (Jote, 2023; Tagkas et al., 2024). Particularly, the nitrogen fertilizers cause the accumulation of nitrates in agricultural products in a way that reflects negatively on human health, causing many diseases, including cancer, kidney failure and others (Kesarwani et al., 2024). This necessitates searching for safe alternatives of synthetic fertilizers such as compost fertilizer. Many studies have shown soil ameliorating and plant growth conditioning potential and other advantages of compost fertilizers as compared to synthetic ones (Chaudhari et al., 2021; Bamdad et al., 2022).

In view of above-mentioned importance of *Narcissus* or daffodil flowers and the Phyto-priming potential of gibberellic acid and compost fertilizer, this laboratory research aimed to assess the effect of different concentrations of gibberellic acid and compost fertilizer on the vegetative growth traits and flowering parameters of the daffodil flowers with an ultimate objective to find out the best combination of gibberellic acid and compost fertilizer for optimum growth and flowering of daffodil flowers.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out in the Department of Plant Production Techniques, Al Mussaib Technical College, Babil Governorate, Iraq during the autumn 2023 and spring 2024. The objective of the study was to determine the effect of compost fertilizer and soaking with gibberellic acid (GA3) on the growth and flowering characteristics of daffodil bulbs. The bulbs of the applied flower-oriental daffodil variety (*Narcissus tazetta orientalis* 'Double Roman') (Figure 1) were procured from one of authenticated flower bulb producers from the city of Mersin, Turkey.

Experimental Layout

Treatments included two different factors. First was soaking the daffodil bulbs in three different concentrations of gibberellic acid for 24 h, i.e., G0 (soaking with distilled water with no gibberellic acid), G1 (soaking with 50 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid solution) and G2 (soaking with 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid solution). The second factor was administration of compost fertilizer in three different rates, i.e., K0 (without any compost fertilizer), K1 (with 15% of pot-mix weight) and K2 (with 30% of pot-mix weight). The soaked bulbs, according to the experiment coefficients, were planted on 10/11/2023 in a 24 × 23 cm pot containing 7 kg of soil mix filled with agricultural medium, and the bulbs were covered after planting with a light layer of soil and were watered daily as per need. All remaining agronomic practices such as irrigation and weeding were carried out whenever needed, and the fertilization was carried out with chemical fertilizer Brusol (neutral NPK) every two weeks once sprayed on the plants.

Table 1. Chemical Properties of Palm Frond Compost

EC (ds/m) 1:10	PH 1:10	N-Total (%)	K (mg/kg)	O.M (%)	C (%)	C/N Ratio
4.75	7.4	2.17	228	76.6	44.42	1/20

Table 2. Chemical and Physical Properties of the Medium Used in the Study

Ece (ds m ⁻¹)	Ph	Nitrogen (mg kg ⁻¹)	Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	Potassium (mg kg ⁻¹)	Organic matter (%)	Sand %	Silt %	Clay %	Texture
3.00	7.3	17.9	11.6	165.3	9.4	62	23	15	Sandy loam

Determination of Plant Growth Parameters

The height of the plant (cm) was calculated from the surface of the pot soil to the top of the flower using a metric measuring tape for all the plants of the experimental unit. Number of leaves per plant were recorded for each plant. Dawn date (days) was calculated by the number of days from the date of planting the bulbs until the emergence of the bud above the soil surface. Leaf length (cm) was determined using a measuring tape for each plant of the experimental unit. The leaf width (cm) was also assessed using a ruler. The flowering age (days) was calculated by choosing two plants randomly from each treatment, where the flowers were picked diagonally from the bottom when the first flower of the flower inflorescence blooms in the early morning, and then the flowers were placed in homogeneous containers containing 100 ml of distilled water and the containers were placed at room temperature (27 °C), and the number of days of staying valid was calculated for each treatment (Figure 2) (Hassan, 2005).

Statistical Analysis

The experiment was conducted following a completely randomized design (CRD) design. The data were analyzed statistically using a factorial analysis of variance (ANOVA), and the treatment means were compared using least significant difference (LSD) post-hoc test at a standard (0.05) probability level (Al-Sahoki & Waheeb, 1990).

Results

Effect of Treatments on Average Plant Height

Results of the study, as shown in Table (3) indicated that there was significant difference between the levels of the both factors regarding the average plant height. The addition of compost fertilizer, particularly by 30%, exceeded the plant height by 30% and exhibited the highest average plant height of 38.19 cm as compared to the control treatment, that produced the lowest plant height average (29.62 cm). As for as the soaking the bulbs with gibberellic acid growth regulator is concerned, highest addition

of compost fertilizer (30% of the pot-mix) exhibited 100 mg L⁻¹ (Table 3) which was significantly highest average (36.83 cm) as compared to the control treatment with the lowest average 29.94 cm. Regarding the interaction of both treatments, the binary treatment containing 30% compost plus soaking with 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid solution) significantly outperformed and gave the highest average plant height (43.33 cm), as compared to the control treatment with zero compost and zero gibberellic acid application with the lowest average plant height of 26.85 cm Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of Compost and Gibberellin on the Average Plant Height (cm) of Daffodils (*Narcissus tazetta* L. var. *Orientalis* ‘Double Roman’)

Compost (%)	Gibberellin (mg L ⁻¹)			Average
	0	50	100	
0	26.85	30.30	31.71	29.62
15	29.32	33.26	35.45	32.68
30	33.66	37.58	43.33	38.19
Average	29.94	33.71	36.83	
	Compost	Gibberellin	Overlap	
LSD	1.09	1.09	1.89	

Effect of Treatments on Average Number of Leaves per Plant

Table (4) indicates that there were significant differences between both of the treatment factors on the number of leaves per plant. The treatment of adding compost material 30% showed the significant and highest average number of leaves per plant (4.82 leaves plant⁻¹), compared to the control treatment without any compost that showed the lowest average (4.30 leaves plant⁻¹). Moreover, treatment with 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid showed significant and highest average of 4.89 leaves per plant while control showed only 4.29 leaves per plant (Table 4). The interaction treatment (30% compost + 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid) significantly outperformed and gave the highest average of 5.54 leaves per plant, as compared to the control treatment with minimum per plant leaves (4.19).

Table 4. Effect of Compost and Gibberellin on the Average Leaf Numbers per Plant of Daffodils (*Narcissus tazetta* L. var. *Orientalis* ‘Double Roman’)

Compost (%)	Gibberellin (mg L ⁻¹)			Average
	0	50	100	
0	4.19	4.25	4.45	4.30
15	4.28	4.32	4.68	4.43
30	4.38	4.54	5.54	4.82
Average	4.29	4.37	4.89	
	Compost	Gibberellin	Overlap	
LSD	0.10	0.10	0.17	

Effect of Treatments on Average Emergence Time

According to the results (Table 5), both treatment factors, either alone or in combination, exerted a significant impact on the plant emergence time duration. The treatment with 30% compost fertilizer exhibited the highest average plant emergence (9.18 days) as compared to the treatment control treatment without any compost fertilizer that showed the lowest average of 7.71 days.

Table 5. Effect of Compost and Gibberellin on the Average Duration of Eruption (Days) of Daffodils (*Narcissus tazetta* L. var. *Orientalis* ‘Double Roman’)

Compost (%)	Gibberellin (mg L ⁻¹)			Average
	0	50	100	

0	7.29	7.54	8.30	7.71
15	7.90	8.11	8.78	8.27
30	8.10	8.39	11.04	9.18
Average	7.77	8.02	9.38	
	Compost	Gibberellin	Overlap	
LSD	0.25	0.25	0.43	

Moreover, soaking with a gibberellic acid growth regulator 100 mg L⁻¹ gave the highest average of 9.38 days as compared to the control treatment with 7.77 days. Moreover, the interaction of both factors (100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid and 30% compost fertilizer application) outperformed with the highest average duration of plant emergence (11.04 days) as compared to the control treatment that showed only 7.29 days plant emergence duration (Table 5).

Effect of Treatments on Average Leaf Length

Results of the study, as shown in Table (6) indicated that there was significant difference between the levels of the both factors regarding the average leaf length. The addition of compost fertilizer, especially one of 30%, could be seen that the result of leaf length was longer and showed the maximum average leaf length of 52.74 cm compared to the control treatment which resulted in the lowest average leaf length of 45.89 cm. The same is true of the soaking of the bulbs with gibberellic acid growth regulator (100 mg L⁻¹) which showed highest average length of leaf (54.68 cm), compared to the control treatment with least average length of leaf (44.11 cm). Regarding the interaction of both treatments, the binary treatment (containing 30% compost fertilizer and soaking with 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid solution) significantly outperformed and gave the highest average leaf length (61.97 cm), as compared to the control treatment with zero compost and zero gibberellic acid application with the lowest average leaf length of 42.19 cm (Table 6).

Table 6. Effect of Compost and Gibberellin on the Average Leaf Length (cm) of Daffodils (*Narcissus tazetta L. var. Orientalis* ‘Double Roman’).

Compost (%)	Gibberellin (mg L ⁻¹)			Average
	0	50	100	
0	42.19	46.07	49.42	45.89
15	44.47	49.04	52.66	48.72
30	45.68	50.58	61.97	52.74
Average	44.11	48.56	52.66	
	Compost	Gibberellin	Overlap	
LSD	1.72	1.72	2.99	

Effect of Treatments on Average Leaf Width

Results analysis showed a significant effect of both treatment factors and their integrated application on average leaf width of daffodil plants (Table 7). The treatment applied to 30% compost fertilizer showed significant effect and recorded the highest mean value of leaf width of 2.31 cm which is higher than the control treatment 0% (2.02 cm). Likewise, effect of gibberellic acid treatment (100mg L⁻¹) was significantly higher as compared to the comparison treatment with the highest average of 2.35cm and lowest average of 1.96cm respectively. Maximum average leaf width (2.59 cm) was recorded for the interaction treatment (30% compost + 100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid) significantly outperformed as compared to the control treatment the lowest average leaf width of 1.83 cm.

Table 7. Effect of Compost and Gibberellin on the Average Leaf Width (cm) of daffodils (*Narcissus tazetta L. var. Orientalis* ‘Double Roman’)

Compost (%)	Gibberellin (mg L ⁻¹)			Average
	0	50	100	
0	1.83	2.06	2.15	2.02
15	1.93	2.13	2.30	2.12

30	2.11	2.24	2.59	2.31
Average	1.96	2.14	2.35	
	Compost	Gibberellin	Overlap	
LSD	0.06	0.06	0.11	

Effect of Treatments on Average Flowering Age of Plants

According to the results (Table 8), both treatment factors, either alone or in combination, exerted a significant impact on the average flowering age of daffodil plants. The treatment with 30% compost fertilizer exhibited the highest average flowering age (15.04 days) as compared to the treatment control treatment without any compost fertilizer that showed the lowest average of 11.25 days. Moreover, soaking with a gibberellic acid growth regulator 100 mg L⁻¹ gave the highest average flowering age of 13.03 days as compared to the control treatment with 12.79 days. Moreover, the interaction of both factors (100 mg L⁻¹ gibberellic acid and 30% compost fertilizer application) outperformed with the highest average flowering age (15.22 days) as compared to the control treatment that showed only 10.78 days of flowering age (Table 8).

Table 8. Effect of Compost and Gibberellin on the Average Flowering Age (Days) of Daffodils (*Narcissus tazetta* L. var. *Orientalis* 'Double Roman')

Compost (%)	Gibberellin (mg L ⁻¹)			Average
	0	50	100	
0	10.78	11.33	11.65	11.25
15	12.75	12.11	12.24	12.36
30	14.84	15.07	15.22	15.04
Average	12.79	12.83	13.03	
	Compost	Gibberellin	Overlap	
LSD	0.06	0.06	0.11	

Discussion

Supplementing with non-synthetic fertilizers such as compost fertilizers and plant growth promoters such as gibberellic acid have been shown as promising environment-friendly strategies to enhance the vegetative growth parameters and flowering characteristics of horticultural crops including cut-flowers (Jokar & Asil, 2021; Adedayo et al., 2022; Hadi & Altaee, 2024). This study aimed to find out the optimum administration of compost fertilizer into the plant soil mix and the soaking of bulbs with gibberellic acid (GA3) for an enhanced growth and performance of *Narcissus* daffodil plants.

Analysis of results obtained during the experiment showed that mixing organic residues into the plant soil in the form of compost fertilizer had significantly increased the vegetative growth traits of daffodil plants, including the average plant height, number of leaves, duration of plant emergence, leaf length and width, and flowering age of the plants. This might be due to the fact that organic residues when mixed with the soil often boost the bioavailability and absorption of essential nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium by the plants. Moreover, these elements have an important role in many physiological and vital activities of the plants. Nitrogen works to stimulate the plant to produce auxins and manufacture proteins, and encourages cell division and stems elongation, and then increase the height of the plant, especially since the growing top contains high concentrations of auxins that work on the elongation of cells (Brahimi, 2011; Hou et al., 2021; Fan et al., 2025). Taiz et al. (2021) have suggested that nitrogen increases the synthesis of chlorophyll and thus increases the carbon metabolism and energy production needed for cell division and elongation. Ahmed et al. (2009) pointed out that the application of organic fertilizers and mulching has increased the plant nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium contents which ultimately enhanced the plant growth, vegetative growth, plant height and photosynthetic activities of plant tissues. Organic fertilizers have an important role in increasing vegetative growth because they improve the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil and increase the readiness of macro

and micronutrients necessary to carry out vital processes within the plant (Mooleki et al., 2004; Verma et al., 2024; Thapa et al., 2025).

Similarly, the results also indicated a significant increase in daffodil plant characteristics by 24 h soaking the bulbs in gibberellic acid 100 mg L⁻¹. This would be due to the gibberellic acid induced phyto-priming resulting into increased and efficient starch conversion to sugar contents and the protein production within the leaves (Lupepsa et al., 2024). The accumulation of these biochemical substances in plant parts enhance many cellular and physiological processes such as cell division and elongation, biosynthesis of cell wall components, RNA and DNA synthesis, and nitrogen fixation (Hayat and Ahmed, 2011; Kurve et al., 2018; Shah et al., 2023).

Our results are in agreement with the findings of some previous researches (El-Naggar, 2010; Nasir, 2017; Jokar & Asil, 2021; El-Attar et al., 2023; Hadi & Altaee, 2024) demonstrating the effectiveness of daffodil bulbs priming with different non-synthetic plant growth promoters such as gibberellic acid and application of compost and other bio-fertilizers on the enhancement of vegetative growth and flowering traits of *Narcissus daffodil* plants.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the overall results of the study that mixing plant soil with compost fertilizer, particularly 30% of the soil mix, and 24 h soaking of bulbs with gibberellic acid, particularly 100 mg L⁻¹, significantly enhanced most of the vegetative growth parameters of the plants including average plant height, leaf number, leaf width, emergence duration and flowering age of the *Narcissus daffodil* plants. Moreover, the integration of both these treatments significantly synergized their effects on plants. These results suggest the future incorporation of this plant growth promoting strategies as alternatives of synthetic chemical fertilizers in the production of daffodils and other cut-flowers.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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